

The relation between 5G electromagnetic waves, temperature and greenhouse gases with Covid 19

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Abstract: Up to date, some observations have shown that there is a direct relation between electromagnetic waves, temperature, humidity, greenhouse gases and Covid 19. However, there isn't any reason for this relation. We propose a model which compares the atmosphere and cellular medium with Urey-Miller system. In a Urey-Miller experiment, there are four main causes in producing amino acids and molecules of life. These causes are:

1. Electromagnetic waves, 2. Temperature, 3. Carbonic, nitric and water molecules 4. Medium. Within the atmosphere, greenhouse gases provided needed carbonic, nitric and water molecules in a Urey-Miller system. These elements also could be found within cells so. On the other hand, in atmosphere, there are many devices like satellites, radio, TV, mobile phones which emit or receive electromagnetic waves. Within a cell, also, ion channels could play the role of electrodes and provide electromagnetic waves. In atmosphere, temperature is changing from a season to another and also from a year to another. Within a cell, also, temperature is changing by increasing or decreasing of molecular densities. Thus, atmosphere and cells have all needed parameters to act like Urey-Miller systems. Now, the question arises that radio wavelengths are longer than cells and how they have any effect on them? To response this question, we should consider the behavior of analog and digital waves. Digital waves are built from a large number of bits with the size around (wavelength/number of bits $\approx 10^{-8}$). According to quantum mechanics, these very short bit waves are emerged in very short time (less than 10^{-16} s) and thus couldn't be detected. However, they can penetrate into cells, play the role of electromagnetic waves in a Urey-Miller experiment, interact with carbonic, nitric and water molecules and produce viral amino acids. Also, these bit waves could join to each other and form electromagnetic hexagonal/pentagonal holes. These holes may be

filled by atoms and form viral RNA bases. On the other hand, analog waves also may join to each other and form a digital waves with a large number of bits. Thus, they could also have a role in induction of viruses. We test the model with observations. We show that countries which are emitter of electromagnetic waves, greenhouse gases or have a sudden change in temperature and wet have more Covid 19 cases respect to others. We formulate Covid 19 incidence rate in terms of temperature, number of bit waves, frequencies and greenhouse distributions.

Keywords: Covid 19; Electromagnetic waves; 5G; Greenhouse gases; Urey-Miller experiment

I. Introduction:

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is the main problem in this year that involve with all people in the world [1]. This is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Totally, this virus is a member of related viruses that cause diseases in mammals and birds. In humans, coronaviruses cause respiratory tract infections that can be mild, such as some cases of the common cold (among other possible causes, predominantly rhinoviruses), and others that can be lethal, such as SARS, MERS, and COVID-19. Among them, COVID-19 is an enveloped viruses with a positive-sense single-stranded RNA genome and a nucleocapsid of helical symmetry. The genome size of coronaviruses ranges from approximately 27 to 34 kilobases, the largest among known RNA viruses [2,3]. Until now, many scientists have tried to find method to cure this disease [4,5], however, without knowing its origin and causes, problem couldn't be solved completely.

Up to date, some effective parameters on the growth rate of Covid 19 have been known. For example, some authors have considered the association between ambient temperature and COVID-19 infection in some cities from China and shown that temperature is an environmental driver of the COVID-19 outbreak in this country [6,7]. Some other authors have clarified the relationship between weather parameters and COVID-19 spread for US and predicted a model of relation for India [8]. Another groups have detected the same relations between weather parameters like temperature, humidity and greenhouse gases for Jakarta, Indonesia [9], Turkey [10] and Bangladesh [11].

Although, many observations show the relation between Covid 19 and electromagnetic waves, however, non of scientists have encourage or maybe allowance to consider this subject scientifically. However, the relation between other viruses and electromagnetic waves have been considered extensively. For example, some authors have shown that exposure to a 50 Hz electromagnetic field induces activation of the Epstein-Barr virus genome in latently infected human lymphoid cells [12]. And also some other authors have considered the radiated waves from viral RNAs and bacterial DNAs [13].

All of these researches and other parallel ones have shown that four causes have more effects on viral diseases. These causes are: 1. Electromagnetic waves, 2. Temperature, 3. Carbonic, nitric and water molecules 4. Medium. All of these factors could be seen in Urey-Miller experiment [14]. It seems that biological systems and earth's atmosphere acts like the Urey-Miller system. In this paper, we consider the relation between Urey-Miller parameters and Covid 19 in real world. The outline of paper is as follows: In section II, we consider the role of bit waves in production of viruses within the Urey-Miller system. In section III, we compare Urey-Miller parameters in different regions of the world and obtain their relations with Covid 19. Last section is devoted to conclusion.

II. The role of bit waves in production of viruses within Urey-Miller systems

Previously, Urey-Miller experiments have shown that four causes are main for production of molecules of life like amino acids, proteins, RNAs and DNAs. These causes are:

1. Electromagnetic wave
2. Temperature
3. Carbonic, nitric and water molecules
4. Media

In this experiment, first water was evaporated, then, mixed with carbonic, nitric and other molecules, after that, mixture experiences an strong electromagnetic radiation and final, medium becomes cooled. It has been observed that some amino acids and molecules of life were emerged.

The Urey-Miller system is comparable with two natural systems: 1. Cells 2. Atmosphere (See figure 1`). Within cells, cellular ion channels play the role of anode and cathode and create an strong electromagnetic waves. In addition, there

are many carbonic, nitric and water molecules within the cell. On the other hand, by increasing density of particles within the cell, temperature is changing. Thus, cellular medium build a type of Urey-Miller system.

Atmosphere also is another type of Urey-Miller system. Greenhouse gases within the atmosphere include CO_2 , CH_4 , molecules of water, O_3 and other molecules.

Also, sun waves, mobile waves, satellite waves and other types of waves play the role of electromagnetic waves within Urey-Miller experiment. On the other hand, by passing a period of time and season, temperature is changed and this gives the best opportunity for creation of new types of life.

Fig 1: Atmosphere of earth and medium within the cell include waves, carbonic, nitric and water molecules and form a Urey-Miller system.

Now, the question arises that which type of electromagnetic waves could have more role in producing molecules of life? There are two types of waves: 1. Analog

waves 2. Digital waves. Analog waves are natural waves which are emitted by charged particles. Digital waves are programmed waves which their length could be divided into some numbers of bits. Each bit has a square shape and store a unit of information (See figure 2).

Fig 2: Analog and Digital waves

Analog waves are more simpler waves and could carry less amount of information respect to digital waves. While, digital waves could act like compacted packages of information. On the other hand, analog waves could join to each other and form a complicated wave. For example, in figure 3, we show that how sin waves could join to each other and form a new form of waves. By joining analog waves, some bits of information are appeared and analog waves convert to digital ones (See figure 4). Also, by joining new digital waves, we can produce different shapes of bits. For example, in figure 5, two square bits join to each other and form a digital hexagonal wave.

Fig 3: Electromagnetic analog waves could join to each other and produce a new complicated wave

Fig 4: N electromagnetic analog waves join to each other and form a digital wave with N bits of information

Fig 5: Two complicated digital waves join to each other and form a new hexagonal wave.

A digital hexagonal wave could be divided into many bits. Each bit has a small length and could pass the cellular gate. We can write:

$$\lambda_{\text{wave}} = N \lambda_{\text{bit}} \tag{1}$$

where λ_{wave} is the wave length, N is the number of bits and λ_{bit} is the bit length. Consequently, bit waves could penetrate into cellular medium. These bits could

join to each other and form hexagonal waves again. These waves could be absorbed by DNA bases and stop or accelerate activities of cells (See figure 6).

Fig 6: Bits of a digital wave have small lengths, pass the cellular membrane and form new digital hexagonal waves within cells.

In figure 7, we bring frequencies of 4 and 5 Generation of mobile waves. Many scientists are afraid that by decreasing wavelengths in 5G, waves could interact with cells and induce viruses and other biological objects within them. However, it seems that compacting information by increasing number of bits within any wavelength is more dangerous. Because, bits could have very small length ($\lambda_{\text{bit}} = \lambda_{\text{wave}}/N$). Also, a bit of information could have a phase frequency which is different from frequency of real wave. We have:

$N \approx 10\text{-}20$ Giga bits

$$d E d t \gg h \rightarrow d E \gg h/d t \rightarrow$$

$$h d v \gg h/d t \rightarrow d v \gg 1/d t, dt \approx N^{-1} t_{\text{period}} \approx 10^{-16}$$

$$\rightarrow d v \approx 10^{16} \rightarrow d v \approx c / \lambda_{\text{bit}} \rightarrow \lambda_{\text{bit}} \approx 10^{-8} \quad (2)$$

Above equation shows that wavelengths of a bit are much smaller than the size of cells. Thus, more than wavelengths, we should worry about bit lengths.

	<u>4G+</u>	<u>5G NSA</u>	<u>5G NSA</u>
THEORET. MAX. DOWNLOAD SPEED	Until 1Gbps	Until 2Gbps	At least 20 Gbps
THEORET. MAX. UPLOAD SPEED	Until 150 Mbps	Until 150 Mbps	Undefined
LATENCY	ca. 30 ms	ca. 15 ms	ca. 1 ms
IN MOBILITY, APPLIABLE QOS SPEED	Until 200 km/h	Until 500 km/h	Until 500 km/h
DENSITY CONNECTED DEVICES	Until 100,000.0 / km ²	Until 1 million / km ²	Until 1 million / km ²
SPECTRUM	<u>800MHz-Band</u> : 60 MHz FDD 2.6GHz-Band: 120 MHz FDD + 50 MHz TDD	<u>700MHz-Band</u> : 3.7GHz-Band: 360 MHz TDD	<u>700MHz-Band</u> : 3.7GHz-Band: 360 MHz TDD
INFRASTRUCTURE	EPC architecture, Radio LTE	EPC architecture, Radio LTE/NR	5G NR architecture with core based network software

Fig7: Comparing wavelengths, number of bits and velocity of 4G and 5G waves.[

<https://www.everythingrf.com/community/5g-frequency-bands>

<https://insightaas.com/radio-spectrum-in-the-5g-wireless-world/>

<https://www.slideshare.net/3G4GLtd/beginners-5g-spectrum-long-version>

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4G and 5G wavelengths are bigger than the size of cells and their analog types couldn't pass the cellular membrane. However, digital waves contain a large number of bits with small sizes which could penetrate into cells and play the role of electromagnetic waves in Urey-Miller experiments. These waves interact with carbonic, nitric and water molecules within the cell and by changing temperature,

produce some types of amino acids. These acids may join to each other and form viral proteins. On the other hand, bit waves may join to each other and form hexagonal/pentagonal holes. These holes could be filled by charged atoms and form hexagonal/pentagonal bases. These bases may join to each other and form viral RNAs. Thus, bit waves have the main role in induction of viruses within cells (See figure 8).

Fig 8: Number of bits in 5G digital waves may be near Giga and their length may be less than 10^{-8} . These waves pass the cellular membranes, interact with carbonic, nitric and water molecules and form a Urey-Miller system. In this system, new proteins and viruses are emerged.

III. Observations: The relation between the Urey-Miller parameters and Covid 19

In previous section, we have compared cells and atmospheres with Urey-Miller systems and propose a model for induction of viruses. Now, we want to examine this model in real world and give some real reasons for its correctness.

First, we should consider different types of sender and receiver radio waves. We shouldn't think that only mobile waves are harmful, but we should regard effects

of other devices so. For example, waves which use in industry of satellites have more frequencies and less wavelengths and thus they could be more effective. Also, although, waves of TV and radio are longer than mobile waves, however, as we show in previous section, if number of bits increases or they join to each other, may produce some bit waves with small lengths and create some problems for cells (See figure 9).

Fig 9: Different types of sender of radio waves and their frequencies

In figure 10. we bring a list of countries which use 5G bands more than others. It is wonderful that most of these countries have huge numbers of Covid 19 cases. To clear this point, in figures 11 and 12, we compared 5G distributions with Covid 19 distributions in the world. Again, we can observe that whenever 5G towers are existed, more number of Covid 19 patients could be observed. Maybe, one ask that some countries don't have 5G, however, their Covid 19 cases are huge. We can response that in those countries, maybe, number of bits increased and compacted waves used. In next steps, we describe this point more.

Fig 10: Countries with upper bands of frequencies[<https://www.everythingrf.com/community/5g-frequency-bands>
<https://www.statista.com/chart/23194/5g-networks-deployment-world-map/>
<https://5g.security/5g/update-to-trusted5g-com-5g-trials-world-map/>

<https://www.worldtimezone.com/5g.html>

<https://www.businessinsider.com.au/the-global-5g-landscape-an-inside-look-at-leading-5g-markets-key-players-and-how-they-are-defining-the-future-of-connectivity-2019-8>]

Trusted5G.com World Map of 5G Field Trials (Updated 1 April 2019)

Fig 11: 5G distributions on the map [

<https://www.trusted5g.com>

<https://www.statista.com/chart/23194/5g-networks-deployment-world-map/>

<https://5g.security/5g/update-to-trusted5g-com-5g-trials-world-map/>

<https://www.worldtimezone.com/5g.html>]

Fig 12: Covid 19 distribution on the map [

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic_by_country_and_territory

<https://reliefweb.int/map/world/covid-19-pandemic-dg-echo-daily-map-20082020>.

<https://reliefweb.int/report/world/new-digital-map-shows-terrible-impact-covid-19-school-meals-around-world>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Epidemiology_of_COVID-19

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Coronavirus-world-map-3-distribution-of-COVID-19-cases-as-of-July-8-2020_fig1_344356974

<https://www.insurancejournal.com/news/international/2020/03/18/561496.htm>

<https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/03/04/mapping-coronavirus-outbreak-infographic/>

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In addition to waves, for building new creatures like viruses in a Urey-Miller system, we need to carbonic, nitric and water molecules. These atoms could be found in greenhouse gases like CO₂, CH₄, N₂O and H₂O. In figure 13, we present top-10 annual CO₂ emitters. It is interesting that these countries usually have more

Covid 19 cases. Also, if we care in map of figure 14 with map of figure 12, we can find scientific relation between greenhouse gases like CO₂ with covid 19. The same relation could be observed between methane emitters in the world and Covid 19 as you can see in map of figure 15. On the other hand, humidity is another main factor in Urey-Miller systems. Water molecules have the main role in producing molecules of life. By increasing humidity, more molecules of water could be existed in a region and more types of life could be observed. For this reason, again, we can find some relations between countries with high degrees of humidity and countries with high funded Covid 19 cases (See figure 16). Another main factor in producing creatures in a Urey-Miller experiments is temperature. As figure 17, shows, temperature of the world changes during last decade. This change is the same of change of temperature in Urey-Miller system. Thus, the world is ready to produce new types of creatures like viruses. Also, changes in temperatures of seasons their selves make the best conditions for producing life molecules. Totally, these causes make the atmosphere and earth similar to Urey-Miller system and make them ready for producing viruses and other types of life. Maybe, one asks that in one country, one of these factors are low, however, we can assert that increasement of other factors compensate it and help in producing viruses.

Top-10 annual CO₂ emitters for the year 2017^[148]

Country	% of global total annual emissions	Total 2017 CO ₂ Emissions (kilotons) ^[149]	Tonnes of GHG per capita ^[150]
China	29.3	10,877,217	7.7
United States	13.8	5,107,393	15.7
India	6.6	2,454,773	1.8
Russia	4.8	1,764,865	12.2
Japan	3.6	1,320,776	10.4
Germany	2.1	796,528	9.7
South Korea	1.8	673,323	13.2
Iran	1.8	671,450	8.2
Saudi Arabia	1.7	638,761	19.3
Canada	1.7	617,300	16.9

Fig 13: A list of countries which emit more CO₂
[\[https://www.britannica.com/science/greenhouse-gas\]](https://www.britannica.com/science/greenhouse-gas)

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/rpapier/2019/12/04/the-worlds-top-10-carbon-dioxide-emitters/>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_carbon_dioxide_emissions]

Fig 14: A map of countries which emit more CO₂
[<https://www.britannica.com/science/greenhouse-gas>]

Methane emissions, 2016

Methane (CH₄) emissions are measured in tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂e) based on a 100-year global warming potential value.

Fig 15: A map of countries which emit more Methane[<https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/methane-emissions>
<https://www.britannica.com/science/greenhouse-gas>]

Fig 17. The Wettest Places in the World[<https://www.climate-charts.com/World-Climate-Maps.html>

<http://scotdir.com/other/rainiest-places-in-the-world>

Fig 18: Temperature change in the world

[<http://www.fao.org/economic/ess/environment/data/temperature-change/en/>]

To test the mode, we should compare the growth rate of Covid 19 in different points of the world. First, we compare USA and Iran as two of top countries in the list of Covid 19 (See figure 18). Although, USA has more cases respect to Iran, however, the growth of incidence rate in both of countries are the same. Maybe, one assume that this similarity is due an electronic war between two countries. Both Iran and USA have industry of satellites and use of microwaves. Also, both of these countries build drones extensively and use of them in military aims. To control these devices, they need to use of some special radio waves. Iran has no 5G yet, however, its scientists learn to compact information in a large number of bit waves. As we have shown before, by increasing number of bits, their sizes become smaller and could penetrate human cells. Also, approximately, each family in Iran has two mobiles. Specially, this country uses of scientific webs like Shad to teach students in their homes and thus, by increasing number of mobile usages, more waves are exchanged which could join to each other and produce more number of bit waves . On the other hand, USA passed an election and some webs like twitter, Facebook and others were used many times. This story isn't ended and wireless usages are increasing. Thus, both countries use a large number of bit waves which may be harmful for people. In addition, both countries are emitters of greenhouse gases which make their conditions close to Urey-Miller systems. Changes in temperatures in some regions of both countries are huge which itself another cause of the emergence of new creatures.

Fig 18: Comparing two countries which involve with electronic war.

[\https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic\]](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic)

To assert our assumptions, we can compare these two countries with their neighbors. For example, Afghanistan is a country between Iran and China, however very small number of Covid 19 (See Figure 19). Also, Iraq which involves with terrorism has smaller Covid 19 cases (See figure 20). Although, because of war, electronic usages increase and number of Covid 19 cases in this country is more than Afghanistan. Maybe, one asks that Afghanistan also involves

with terrorism. To response, we may guess that terrorists in Irag have more high tech devices and use of bit waves better.

Fig 19: Afghanistan is between Iran and China, however has minor cases of covid

19. [<https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19>

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic]

Fig 20: Iran has more covid 19 cases respect to Irag which involves with terrorism[<https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19>

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic]

As we have referred war causes to an increase in number of wave usages. Another example, could be Azerbaijan and Armenia. These two countries have approximate the same the growth rate in number of Covid 19 cases, although, some differences could be observed. Also, these countries are near Iran and Russia which have more number of patients in this region (See figure 21). Russia is one of strongest countries in building satellites and other types of electronic devices. This country like USA and Iran tries to build high tech electronic devices and compete in space

and earth. For this reason, bit waves are using a large number of times in this country and consequently, number of Covid 19 cases grows. On the other hand, Russia has different regions which each region has an special weather. Some regions of Russia has a high percent of humidity and makes the good conditions for producing new types of life like viruses. Another main industrial country is China. This country is one of emitter of greenhouse gases. Wuhan in this country is near a river and in some seasons has a high percent of humidity. Also, China like USA and Russia has a high technology in producing satellites. Most of mobile phones in the world are produced by Chinese companies. Thus, this country has the most usage of bit waves which summing with humidity and grean house gases make the best conditions for producing life molecules like viruses (See figure 22).

Fig 21: Two another example of countries which experience electronic war [<https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19>]

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic

Fig 22: China controls covid19; while Russia couldn't.

[\https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic

Europe has many industrial countries and thus has the main role in producing greenhouse gases. Also, these countries have high electronic technologies and in each time, one satellite from one of them goes to space. They are using of 5G with Giga number of bits. These bit waves in addition to greenhouse gases enter into biological systems and make the best conditions for producing different types of creatures like viruses. For this reason, you can see that Italy, Spain, France AND Germany have more number of Covid 19 cases (See figures 23 and 24).

Fig 23: Two main countries in Europe which involve with covid 19.

[\[https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19\]](https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19)

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic

Fig 24: Another example of industrial countries involving with covid 19.

[\https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic

In Africa, industrial country like South Africa has more number of Covid 19 cases in compare with Egypt which is a non-developing one (See figure 25). South Africa has a beautiful view and attracts more number of passengers. Consequently, number of mobile usages or bit waves increases and Covid 19 cases grow.

Fig 25: Comparing covid 19 in two main countries of Africa.

[<https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19>

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic]

Totally, industry, weather, mobile usage, humidity and wet and also greenhouse gases play the main role in increasing number of Covid 19 CASES. Countries like Chad, Brunei and Albania which have less interaction with the world, has less number of Covid 19 cases (See figure 26). While industrial countries like China, USA, Russia, India, Iran, Italy, France and Germany have more number of Covid 19 cases or are its generator.

Fig 26: Covid 19 within countries with less interaction in the world.

[\https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19

https://support.google.com/websearch/answer/9814707?p=cvd19_statistics&hl=en-IR&visit_id=637436279918927458-3310884623&rd=1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic

To formulate these observations, we need to more exact datas. However, as a first step in this field, we can assume that the incidence rate for Covid 19 cases have below relations with temperature:

$$d(\text{Incidence rate}) / (T - T_0) \rightarrow d T / T$$

or

$$\text{Incidence rate} \rightarrow (T - T_0) \log(T / T_0) \quad (3)$$

In above equation T_0 is the normal temperature of medium. Above equation shows that any change in temperature causes to a change in evolutions of biological system and increases or decreases of incidence rate for Covid 19 (See figure 27).

Fig 27: Dependency of incidence rate in terms of temperature[Hypothetical model]

In addition to temperature, we should regard greenhouse gases so. Because these gases include carbonic and nitric molecules which are main causes in Urey-Miller experiments. We can write:

$$d(\text{Incidence rate}) \rightarrow d \text{ greenhouse} / \text{ greenhouse}$$

or

$$\text{Incidence rate} \rightarrow \log(\text{greenhouse} / \text{greenhouse}_0) \quad (4)$$

Where greenhouse_0 is the normal gas radiation rate. In Fig 28, we draw incidence rate in terms of CO_2 emission rate. The negative values for incidence rate aren't real and show a non normal conditions. By increasing emission rate, more needed carbons for producing molecules of life could be provided and the number of Covid 19 cases grow.

Fig 28: Dependency of incidence rate in terms of CO_2 emission rate [Hypothetical model]

We can obtain the similar equation for humidity so:

$$\text{Incidence rate} \rightarrow -A \log(1 - \text{humidity} / \text{humidity}_0) \quad (5)$$

Where humidity_0 is the high degrees of wet/humidity. It is clear that by increasing humidity, number of water molecules grows and medium become more similar to Urey-Miller experiments. In these conditions, more amino acids and other life molecules could be emerged and number of cases increases (See figure 29).

Fig 29: Dependency of incidence rate in terms of humidity rate[Hypothetical model]

We can assume that the relation between number of bits, wavelengths and incidence rate is also logarithmic:

$$d(\text{Incidence rate}) / (\text{number of bits}) \rightarrow$$

$$d(\text{number of bits/wavelength}) / (\text{number of bits/wavelength})$$

or

$$\text{Incidence rate} \rightarrow (\text{number of bits}) \log(\text{number of bits/wavelength}) \quad (6)$$

It is clear that by increasing number of bits, wavelength is divided into smaller bit waves and these waves could pass the cellular membranes, interact with carbonic, nitric and water molecules and produce extra amino acids. These amino acids could join to each other and form viruses (See Figure 30). Bit waves are not only small but time of their life is very small such as we can't detect them.

Fig 30: Dependency of incidence rate in terms of number of bits [Hypothetical model]

In addition to bit waves, waves themselves could use of quantum tunneling and enter into cells. We can write below relation for their tunneling:

$$\text{Incidence rate} \rightarrow (\text{frequency})e^{\text{frequency}/100000} \quad (7)$$

Obviously, by increasing frequency, wavelengths decrease and waves become smaller. These small waves could penetrate into cells and play the role of electromagnetic waves in a Urey-Miller system.

Consequently, more amino acids are emerged and incidence for the emergence of Covid 19 rate increases.

Fig 31: Dependency of incidence rate in terms of frequency [Hypothetical model]

To obtain the real Incidence Rate in a theoretical model, we should regard all factors together. We can write:

$$\text{Incidence rate} \rightarrow -A(T-T_0)\log(T/T_0) \log(\text{greenhouse}/ \text{greenhouse}_0) \log(1-\text{humidity}/\text{humidity}_0) (\text{frequency})e^{\text{frequency}/10000} (\text{number of bits})\log(\text{number of bits/wavelength}) \quad (8)$$

Above equation shows that for the emergence of Urey-Miller system within the atmosphere of a region and within the human cells, we need to provided sufficient temperature, greenhouse gases, humidity, number of bit waves and smaller waves. By creation of Urey-Miller system, some amino acids are emerged which could be the origin of viral proteins. Maybe in one region, one of these factors decreases, however other factors grow and our desirable system is produced.

Conclusion

Recently, many questions have arised about relations between electromagnetic waves, temperature, greenhouse gases and Covid 19. However, non of these questions haven't responded very good. Mostly, any connection between waves

and viruses have been denied. Because, radio waves or mobile waves couldn't pass the cell membrane and thus, there have no any effect. This is a wrong imagination from waves. They are quantum objects and couldn't be compared with classical ones. There are two types of electromagnetic waves. Analog and digital ones. A digital waves could be formed from a large number of bits which each of them only take an small size of wavelength. These waves could be separated only for a short time, for example 10^{-16} second from real wave and have a size less than (10^{-8}). These bit waves could pass the cellular membranes and interact with DNAs. Analog waves also join to each other and form a digital wave with a large number of bits. Thus, more than wavelengths, number of waves and digital bits are main. Countries which have more electromagnetic radiations have more Covid 19 patients. The same relation could be observed between temperature, greenhouse gases and Covid 19. Now, the question arises that what how these factors play the role in induction of viruses. To response this question, we should compare atmosphere and cells with Urey-Miller system. Electromagnetic waves act like waves in Urey-Miller systems, greenhouse gases provide nitric, carbonic and water molecules. Also, changes in temperature of atmosphere and cells acts like changes in temperature within the Urey-Miller experiment. Countries which emit more electromagnetic waves and greenhouse gases, make the best conditions for induction of viruses. Because bit waves penetrate within the cells, interact with nitric, carbonic and water molecules and produce viral proteins. We have formulated the relation between Urey-Miller parameters and Covid 19.

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